

IQTISODIYOT VA ZAMONAVIY TEXNOLOGIYA

Onlayn ilmiy jurnal

Jild: 03 Nashr: 07 (2024)

www.mudarrisziyo.uz

ISSN: 2992-8907

MEASURES TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF BANKING ACTIVITIES

L. A. Urinov

Faculty of Andijan State University of Economics in Tashkent State University of Economics

Annata: *This study explores key approaches to improving the efficiency of commercial banks by reducing costs.*

Keywords: *Banking efficiency, financial resources, efficiency improvement programs, profitability, competitiveness, bank expenses.*

Traditionally, the first direction of cost reduction is with personnel expenses, and this is known to all of us because their share of operating expenses is usually 50-55%. It's time to think about the productivity of employees and the technologies and processes used. In general, the main areas of commercial banking development should include:

1. Strengthening positions in regional and regional markets.
2. Steady growth in the volume of services.
3. To ensure optimal balance between yield and risk while minimizing the negative impact of adverse environmental factors.
4. Development of economic, information security, and bank risk management systems.
5. Maintaining the bank's capitalization at the appropriate level.
6. Balancing the interests of shareholders, creditors, insurers, and other interested parties.
7. Developing comprehensive relationships with customers, including studying their needs, developing and launching new banking products, improving technology, and improving the quality of service.
8. Development of a material and technical base according to the size and type of activity. The following basic principles can be applied to prevent possible errors in designing and implementing a cost-reduction program.
 1. The first step in developing the program should, at first glance, be a step that has nothing to do with costs. This step must be approved by shareholders for the next 3-5 years, considering the main objectives and directions of the bank's development, and the changes made. For example, if the bank's shareholders see the prospects for business development, a retail project launched several years ago or a small business launch project would be the first victim of a cost-cutting program. However, if the bank's future is in providing banking services to individuals, the area and focus for optimization will be transferred to other areas of banking activity. Thus, it provides a solid correlation between the first-leaning program and the goals set by the shareholders.

2. Despite a significant share of employee expenses in operating expenses, there is no need to focus solely on that item. It is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of using the office space of banks. An indicator that is actively used by chain retailers, that is, "sell for a square meter," can help here. In the case of financial institutions, this figure may be as follows: "Operating income for the unit of the Bank's control point" or "Assets/Liabilities of Point of Existence on the Units." Do not neglect the cost of buying ads, IT, and stationery. There is no exception that cost analysis and measures to reduce them can lead to a revision and significant change in the Bank's business model. Senior managers of the bank should be prepared for this.
3. The success of the cost-cutting program largely depends on the commitment of senior management and its division into support for change. Therefore, for successful implementation, the person responsible for the management of the bank is required, who be personally accountable for achieving the result. Ideally, two or three managers, each of whom will play a role in the implementation of the changes, could be appointed: one acting as a "diplomat" and trying to inform all stake leaders about the need for change; The latter should become familiar with the details of how the bank works and act as an "expert" to confirm the feasibility and implementation of the proposed changes. The third is the "leader" of these changes and constantly monitors the performance of tasks. All of these roles can be combined in one position, but it is very rare. Thus, the third provision speaks of the need to form a team of senior managers who are personally responsible for the implementation of the approved program. It is also important to understand that the cost-cutting program can only be effectively developed if the correct calculation is provided and the costs are shared between bank boards. Without this element, it is impossible to make management decisions in this direction and compare the activities of a particular bank with the market. Conversion of bank branch networks into highly computerized differentiated systems for the sale of paid products has enabled US banks to transfer administrative functions of branches to administrative centers; 6 times the occupied territory, 2 times the number of employees, and 25% reduction in household expenses. The number of bank branches has fallen by 20% due to the introduction of telephone customer service (about 15 million people) in France. For banks, keeping and buying customers is vital. According to Western analysts, customer retention accounts for only 25 percent of the cost of acquiring new customers. According to surveys, 78% of customers refuse banking services. The main reason for this is unsatisfactory pricing and lower quality of services provided. Western credit institutions offering online banking products with various technical devices and telecom lines can maintain their image and popularity. 3 programs were selected by grouping and evaluating the programs and methods for reducing bank expenses. The first program to reduce costs and improve the efficiency of banking activities has 5-10 percent potential without an organizational restructuring of the bank, i.e. without global changes, replacing plastic cards, cash withdrawal, opening accounts, applying for loans, etc., with automated computer systems, replacing personnel who perform monotonous work, such as transferring ordinary bank employees to more necessary activities invited, For example, the provision of banking services, the presentation of banking products and the general consideration of benefits, the calling of potential customers to credit or registration of salary cards, automation of banking services and appointment of consultants and staff whose tasks include checking and maintaining the status of technical means. The second cost reduction program is rental expenses, which have the potential to reduce costs by 5-20%, costs can be reduced by revising lease agreements, but when revising, difficulties with existing lease agreements can arise, it is also possible to reduce the number of expenses by reducing rented space, it is recommended that you consider the

effectiveness of the bank's office in reducing the lease area, There is also an appropriate concept, such as "income per square meter," which according to the profitability analysis, can be reduced to unprofitable branches or banking institutions. With a serious and persistent approach to this program, you can reduce rental costs by up to 20%. Third cost reduction program outsourcing (transferring any process or function using an external source) can reduce costs by up to 10%, cost reduction is possible by transferring certain functions to third parties, for which this activity is the main one, cheaper for bank expenses, may be functions such as searching and training outsourcing personnel, collecting cash, strategic with service providers In establishing partnerships, the Bank has the opportunity to obtain additional income from strategic partnerships, such as building cleaning, transportation services, etc. In this context, it is necessary to optimize processes before outsourcing operations, functions, and services.

Literature:

1. Kropin Y.A. Money, Credit, Banks.—Moscow: Yurayt, 2016. P. 136.
2. Yaroslavskaya, E.V. Development and analysis of innovative solutions in the banking sector / E.V. Yaroslavskaya.—Moscow: LAP Lambert Academic Journal, 2015.-112.
3. Sinki D., Levinzon A.I.—M.: Alpine. Business Books, 2016.-1018.
4. Vikulov V. S. Contextual Approach to the Development of Innovative Networks of a Commercial Bank // Financial Management. 2004. No. 5. 106-121
5. Banking and Banking / Ed. D. E. n., Professor I. T. Balabanov. - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2001 year. Management of the bank. Lesson / Ed. D. e. n., Professor O. I. Lavrushina. 3rd edition, revised and added M.: Knorus, 2009